

Poem by Dr. S. Esther Juliet Sujatha

Beauty of Birds

Feathers dipped in dawn and dusk,
They paint the sky with silent grace.
Songs ripple through the morning air,
Nature's poetry finds a voice.
Wings teach freedom without words,
Colors bloom where hope resides.
In every flight and tender call,
The earth learns how to smile.

Bio:

Dr. S. Esther Juliet Sujatha is Associate Professor of English at Sri Sarada College for Women (Autonomous), with over twenty-five years of experience in teaching, research, and academic mentorship. A bilingual poet writing in English and Tamil, her creative work reflects ecological awareness and a deep engagement with social and cultural issues.

Her academic interests include Indian Writing in English, Subaltern Studies, and Dalit Literature, with a particular focus on literature as a medium for social transformation. She has guided thirteen M.Phil. scholars and has published research articles and poetry in national and international journals. Her doctoral research, *Yearning for an Egalitarian Society: A Thematic Study of the Select Works of Bama*, reflects her sustained engagement with questions of social justice and marginalised voices.

Dr. Sujatha is also an accomplished translator from English into Tamil and editor of *Cultural Perspectives in Modern Literature*. She has organised international poetry competitions on themes of nature and education, and was awarded the **Best Assistant Professor (GMRAF Awards, 2020)** in recognition of her academic excellence.